

Craft Activity of Women in Jizzak Region

Tursunova Dildora¹

¹ Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Abstract:

The article talks about the support of women's activities in the reforms carried out in our country today, the work carried out in this regard in the Jizzakh region, the participation of regional women in the fields of handicrafts and entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Handicrafts, "Hunarmand" association, national crafts, entrepreneurship, vocational training of women.

The reforms carried out in our country today are reflected in all regions of our republic. These reforms are gaining practical importance in Jizzakh region as well. Jizzakh region is one of the regions located in the central part of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which has a great political, economic, and spiritual position, where science, culture, and tourism have flourished. Jizzakh is distinguished by its long history, unique culture, life and activities. At the same time, the hardworking and enterprising people of the oasis have been working on the basis of constant research and effective use of opportunities. In this place, the activity of women of the region, especially their role in the development of national crafts is important.

The Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of supporting women and ensuring their active participation in the life of society"[1.Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of supporting women and ensuring their active participation in the life of society." New Uzbekistan // March 5, 2021.] and the Cabinet of Ministers "Employment of women, Based on the directions defined in the Resolution "On measures to further improve the system of entrepreneurship development among them", the entrepreneurship and business activities of women are being supported in the region. Under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev, on March 19, five important initiatives aimed at increasing attention to youth, involving them in culture, art, physical education and sports, instilling in them the skills of using information technologies, promoting reading among young people, and ensuring employment of women and girls were announced. put forward.[2.The President defined important

tasks for raising the morale of young people and meaningfully organizing their free time. People's word // March 19, 2019.] The number of young people who are effectively using the opportunities created in our country and have their place in society is increasing. In particular, in the last 9 months of 2022, 3 thousand 305 young people completed entrepreneurship training courses and received a special certificate in Jizzakh region.

Handicraft is one of the specific areas of youth employment in the region. According to the information of the "Hunarmand" association of Jizzakh region, there are 1,118 artisans working in the region. 448 of them are young people under 30 years old. Employment of young men and women is ensured by teaching crafts inherited from ancestors.

In particular, at the moment, 172 artisans in the region are establishing "Master-Apprentice" schools and educating 527 apprentices. Special training courses are being held in 299 neighborhood assemblies in the cities and districts of Jizzakh region in order to bring the system of working with families and women to a new level, to effectively organize the activities of the persons responsible for neighborhood work and to ensure mutual cooperation. [3.Bringing the system of working with women to a new level is a vital necessity, People's word// April 27, 2022] In cooperation with the Chamber of Commerce and Industry, the Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship, business women "Entrepreneur" and "Hunarmand" associations, women's entrepreneurship centers, as well as other non-governmental non-profit organizations, more than 60 different model "Business plans" specific to women's entrepreneurship were created. ” projects and handouts were prepared and delivered to the locations. 116 participants from Jizzakh region studied at the Higher School of Business and Entrepreneurship.

Today, women's entrepreneurship centers with the status of non-profit organizations are operating in our country.

These centers perform the following tasks:

- attract women who want to engage in entrepreneurship to the centers and assist in organizing entrepreneurship activities;
- formation of women's skills in organizing and running their own business, consulting assistance in the preparation of business ideas, including preparation of a project business plan, selection and application of various taxation regimes, accounting, modern information technologies organization of training in use and other directions;
- in necessary cases, to help women entrepreneurs who are starting their activities to allocate space from vacant buildings in neighborhoods;
- to provide necessary advice and practical assistance to women entrepreneurs and women who express a desire to engage in entrepreneurship in setting up their own business, including finding reliable partners, assisting in the purchase of mini-technologies and equipment, sales of manufactured products help to be done;
- providing practical assistance to women artisans who are working informally in using taxes and other types of benefits and obtaining preferential loans through registration and membership of the "Hunarmand" association.

Women who express a desire to engage in entrepreneurship are trained according to a special training program based on a list formed by the district (city) governor and the district (city) women's committee.

Jizzakh region has its own values and traditions-cultural heritage. On the order of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the intangible cultural heritage of the Jizzakh region was studied during the expedition conducted by the Uzbek culture and art promotion center "Lifelong Heritage" within the framework of the state social order project on the topic "Protection of

intangible cultural heritage elements of Uzbekistan". He met directly with the custodians and providers of knowledge and skills related to intangible cultural heritage in three areas: performing arts, cooking, crafts, and got acquainted with their activities. It should be recognized that there are many people engaged in folk art in Jizzakh region. Craftsmen in the province who are engaged in such types of handicrafts as national embroidery, pearl handicrafts, blacksmithing, saddle-harness making, weaving, thread spinning, dry farming, and wool spinning are worthy of praise.

In conclusion, it should be noted that the economic opportunities of Jizzakh region are wide, and further development of the people's entrepreneurship, especially women's work in the field of handicrafts, is of great importance.

LIST OF REFERENCES

1. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further improve the system of supporting women and ensuring their active participation in the life of society." New Uzbekistan // March 5, 2021.
2. Bringing the system of working with women to a new level is a vital necessity, People's word//April 27, 2022
3. AbdukadirovS. Traditions and transformations of Jizzakh oasis carpet-making (historical-ethnological research) Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) dissertation in historical sciences 2023.
4. Information of "Hunarmand" association of Jizzakh region. Jazz 2022.